

EXAMINING THE IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGY ON COLLEGE LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS

Student: Abdurakhim Turakulov,

Kimyo International University in Tashkent

Scientific Adviser: Fozilbek Orzibekov,

Senior Lecturer, Head of English Language Department, Kimyo International University in Tashkent

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15488416>

Annotation: This article provides information about the role of technology in the higher education system. On this topic, questionnaires were conducted among students of KIMYO INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY IN TASHKENT, Samarkand branch and information about the results of the questionnaire and how many students participated is also provided. The beneficial and harmful aspects of technology for students are also revealed. What results and measures should be taken are also presented in this article. In conclusion, there is information about the fact that modern education cannot be imagined without technology and what restrictions there are on the use of technology in the higher education system. Sufficient information is also provided about the harm that technology has on the lifestyle of students.

Key words: Technology, modern education, impact of technology, student, higher education, student engagement.

Introduction

Students, teachers, and other professionals studying in higher education institutions now use modern technologies extensively. Today's students need to be able to use technology well in order to study in higher education. Today's higher education students all have their own technological learning tools, for example, almost all students have computers, wireless headphones, phones, tablets, and various other

technological devices. Therefore, teachers and students are learning from each other and using technology to find the information they need. This also allows teachers to teach the education system to students very well. Modern technologies are creating very convenient conditions for students.

For example, students can take online classes from home and watch various videos. 90% of students in higher education use modern technologies in some way. As technology becomes an integral part of everyday life, high fuel prices are also pushing students to choose online or hybrid courses (Allen & Seaman, 2008). In addition, many students expect students to use Internet technologies, believing that this will make the learning process more convenient and effective (Salaway & Caruso 2008). The above examples also contain information about the use of technology and modern technologies. The following is a more complete list.

Literature review

Since the early 2000s, web applications have become the standard platform for distance learning courses and learning management systems (Parsad & Lewis, 2008). The widespread adoption of digital technologies and the popularity of online courses have prompted many researchers to study how the Internet and web-based educational technologies affect student engagement and learning outcomes (Braten & Stroms, 2006; Kuh & Hu, 2001; Robinson & Hullinger, 2008; Zhou & Zhang, 2008). The concept of student engagement is not new to educators. Many years of research have shown that the impact on a student's academic performance is largely determined by where and by whom they are exposed to college (Austin, 1993; Kuh, 2004; Pace, 1980; Pascarella & Perenzini, 2005). These examples show that in the modern educational system, online classes, the Internet, various websites are all modern technologies. Developments in computer and communication technologies also have a significant impact on the field of education. In the last decade, Internet-based online education has developed rapidly to create additional learning opportunities for non-traditional students (Welsh Wanberg, Brown, & Simmering, 2003). Blended learning, a form of technology-enhanced learning, combines online and traditional classroom teaching methods (Osduthorpe & Graham, 2003; Polin, 2004).

The examples above show that the use of technology and social media has increased in recent years. Another thing that is mentioned in the examples is the increasing number of online classes. This also shows that technology has been well developed. This shows that technology has been well developed.... As technology is constantly evolving, many students are afraid of it interfering too much in the learning process. Berrett, Murphy & Sullivan (2012) point out that there are several problems when integrating technology in the classroom. These problems can be related to hardware and software failures, device failures, curriculum issues, or teachers who feel insecure about using technology.

These examples show that all students and teachers can be hesitant or unable to use technology. Teachers can set specific tasks for their students to use technology to avoid such problems. Sincar (2013) also emphasizes this and says that resistance to the use of technology in the classroom often comes from the students themselves.

Students often resist because they feel uncomfortable using technology or are faced with the need to change their pedagogy.

Sincar's point is very correct, because most students openly prohibit the use of technology. Students taught by such teachers may also face problems in using technology in the future. Students who are afraid of using technology should be explained that using technology is very useful. The opinions of 4 experts were presented, and most of the experts were skeptical about the useful aspects of technology. However, information was also provided about teachers and students who cannot use technology well. There was also limited information about teachers who have the necessary experience in using technology in higher education to provide their students with the necessary knowledge and skills. The following sections also provide concepts about technology.

Methodology

A survey was conducted for this study. The questions are presented below:

1. What do you understand by the impact of technology on the higher education learning environment?
2. What are the benefits of technology for teachers?
3. What should students using technology pay attention to?
4. What are the limitations of using technology in modern education?
5. What is your opinion on the full use of technology in the education system?

The following questions were asked in the survey. The questions were mainly based on the impact of technology on higher education. Students who participated in the survey were students of the Samarkand branch of Kimyo International University in Tashkent. 2 groups of students participated in the survey. The total number of students from 2 groups is 25. Group 1 was English Education 3rd course students. 12 students from this group expressed their opinions on the questions. The students of the 2nd group were students of the English Education 2nd course. A total of 13 students from this group participated in the survey. In order to ensure the safety of the students who participated in the survey, information about them was not provided.

2. However, information about the opinions given by 25 students will definitely be provided. This survey was conducted in written form on the Telegram application. The students of the English Education 2 course submitted it in written form on paper.

Findings

The answers received from 25 students are as shown above. 90% of the students answered the 5 questions positively. 10% of the students said that they did not have enough knowledge about modern technologies. 20 students gave complete information in the written questionnaire. 10% of the students, that is, 5 students, answered 2 questions differently, while some students answered 1 question. Therefore, 10% of the students were said to not have enough knowledge about technologies. Since 20 students answered the questions and added new ideas, it was concluded that the questions were answered completely. The opinions of 20 students were almost the same, all of them expressed positive opinions. There were also some who expressed negative opinions, which will be reviewed in other sections with their solutions.

Discussion

Here we have also got acquainted with the results of the research. The answers were also very well presented. Almost all students expressed positive opinions about technology. Examples of 20 students who had almost the same opinion were given. We will discuss the ideas a little. The students expressed very useful ideas about the importance of technology in higher education.

The students said that it increases the efficiency of education and creates new opportunities for teachers and students. This is a very correct idea. The development of technology increases the efficiency of education and creates wide opportunities for teachers and students. These ideas are very relevant in the current era of advanced technologies. Another idea was also discussed. For example, many students said that the most useful aspect of technology is online classes. Online classes are one of the most useful methods in modern education. This shows that technology is well developed in such classes. Students also emphasized that technology is very important for teachers. They also wrote that it is important for teachers to use technology to teach more effectively and that it is very easy for students to understand these lessons. Indeed, technology is very important for teachers today.

Recommendation

Research was conducted. Surveys were conducted. Students were also introduced to their opinions. Students mentioned both positive and negative aspects in a written questionnaire. A lot of information was provided about the positive aspects. It was also emphasized that the modern education system cannot do without the use of technology. However, very little information was provided about the negative aspects of technology. One of the students mentioned this in a written questionnaire. Technology also has negative aspects. If students rely on technology, their independent thinking becomes very weak. Serious problems can be observed in human health as a result of the use of technological tools in the learning process.

In order to prevent such problems, the student also brought solutions to these problems. It was mentioned that in order for the scope of independent thinking to not be narrowed, it is necessary to read various e-books using technology, play games that improve electronic brain activity, and perform electronic memory exercises. Regarding health, the need for educational tools that fully ensure the necessary safety when using technology was also mentioned. For example, the need to wear reflective glasses when using a computer, phone, or tablet was also mentioned.

Conclusion

In conclusion, modern education has reached a level where it is impossible to imagine without technology. Therefore, it is necessary to create the opportunity to live in the future without difficulties by using these tools correctly. If the 21st century is considered an era of advanced technologies, then all professionals should know how to use technology. Information about technology was also provided in the research conducted. The questionnaires were thoroughly studied and solutions to the problems were provided. It was learned that, even if it is small, there is a role of technology in higher education.

References:

1. Abduraximov. Z. Mirzaxidov. O. 2021 yil 5, dekabr. Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida yangi texnologiyalarning o'rni. Студенческий научный журнал выпуск No.42 (170) часть-5. <https://sibac.info/archive/journal/student/42>
2. Chen. P. et. al. 31 July 2009. The impact of web - based learning technology on college student engagement. Computers & Education 54 (2010) 1222- 1232. www.elsevier.com/locate/compedu
3. Wood. E. et. al. 6 June 2011. Examining the impact of off- task multi- tasking with technology on real- time classroom learning. Computer & Education 58 (2011) 365- 374. www.elsevier.com/locate/compedu
4. Star. Sh. The Impact of technology on student learning